

Speculation on the Quantum Wavefunction in the Classical Limit

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Newtonian mechanics often employs a potential $V(x)$ such that $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)^2 + V(x) = E$ ((1)) where $v(x)$ is velocity. Mathematically $V(x)$ is defined at each x , but in reality there should be a tiny cutoff i.e. finite dx . Newtonian mechanics makes use of the idea of small dx lengths which tend to 0 mathematically. To first order $v(x)$ is constant within a dx range, but the overall mathematics is continuous instead of discrete. Thus there is a continuous equation ((1)) for conservation of energy.

A photon may be described by an eclectic field varying as $\cos(-Et+px)$. In terms of wavelengths $\exp(ipx)$ is often used as a mathematical convenience and noncontinuous behaviour is not an issue. For example in refraction, momentum = $\hbar/\text{wavelength}$ abruptly changes and one straight line path is joined to another with a different slope. $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with repeatable wavelength patterns with a single wavelength representing a spatial distribution/ (kind of probability) region.

A particle with rest mass may also be described by $\exp(ipx)$ which suggests a characteristic length \hbar/p . Within this length (i.e. at each x point which exist within \hbar/p) the particle has p and $p^2/2m$. Thus for a square well potential there is conservation of energy at each x point even though there is a wavelength in the problem. This is fine for a constant momentum, but what about a potential $V(x)$ which implies p must change at each dx region? $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar d/dx$ which is linked to spatial invariance. It manifests itself physically by interference (e.g. two slits) which again involves non-smooth motion (i.e. one compares rays with completely different slopes). The characteristic length \hbar/p is fixed and associated with a single p , yet momentum is supposed to change from one x point to the next. \hbar/p does not fit within a single dx and this is a problem.

Quantum mechanics remedies this issue by allowing for a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s i.e. $W(x)$ = wavefunction = $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that energy conservation is forced at each x . Thus one combines the idea of wavelength (which is physical) with energy conservation which is also physical. A consequence of this, however, is that $-i\hbar dW/dx / W$ leads to a strange average momentum which is not the square root of $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ as well as discrete energies. A mathematical benefit is that one has a continuous differential equation, namely the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

The question we ask is: What happens in the so-called classical limit? In the nonrelativistic case this leads to Newtonian mechanics in which there is no wavelength. How does the wavelength disappear so to speak? We suggest (as has been suggested often in the literature and textbooks) that the wavelengths in $W(x)$ may become extremely tiny so as to not be detected easily in classical length scales. Mathematically the time-independent Schrodinger equation holds and there is a smooth $W(x)$ at all points, but we suggest that this smoothness may not be necessary because it is not found in refracting light. If the wavelength is tiny compared to small dx regions in the classical limit, then many wavelengths of a given p fit into dx . Thus the idea of spatial invariance approximately holds within dx and there is no issue of the wavelength spilling out of the dx region as it does when it is comparable to the size of the system as in quantum bound problems. Thus within dx a single p with many (or at least several)

wavelengths holds and there is a single p . The kinetic energy is $pp/2m$ and the potential $V(x)$ where x is in the center of dx . One may think of p changing abruptly (nonsmoothly) at the boundary of one dx with another such that conservation of energy holds. Thus one has p wavelengths which do not spill out of dx and give an approximate sense of spatial invariance together with energy conservation. The only loss is that of a smooth wavefunction, but it is not clear that such smoothness is a requirement. $V(x)$ is physically associated with a limiting dx length (at which the concept of $V(x)$ does not hold, but rather there are stochastic hits) and if one expands this length i.e. chooses a much bigger dx in keeping with classical scales, it seems that there should not be a problem. It as if $V(x)$ delivers an impulse hit at each dx junction (like a series of different media in refraction)..

This approach leads to the decoherence of wavelengths in the classical limit.

The Notion of Potential

A potential $V(x)$ is used in Newtonian mechanics, special relativity and quantum mechanics (both nonrelativistic and relativistic). $V(x)$, however, is a mathematical approximation because it holds for all x points and physically should break down at some dx length. This dx length, however, is tiny compared to both classical and quantum lengths. Thus the idea of $dx \rightarrow 0$ is reasonable. Newtonian mechanics uses the notion of dx to define velocity (momentum) which is then used in a conservation of energy equation:

$$.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

The idea, however, seems to be that $v(x)$ is constant within a tiny dx region thus defining kinetic energy $.5mv(x)v(x)$ within that region which may be added to $V(x)$ to yield a constant energy. At the same time the particle accelerates, but this does not appear within a dx region when considering conservation of energy. It is manifested by a different $v(x)$ in the next dx region. Thus it seems that for tiny dx regions, one may have a nonsmooth picture of a constant $p(x)$ within dx receiving an instantaneous impulse at the junction of two dx regions just as p changes with light at the interface of two media. The point we wish to make is that once one has chosen a tiny dx length which approximates "0" compared to other lengths in the problem, one does not need to have mathematical smoothness within this region necessarily. One need only enforce conservation of energy in each dx region so "energy" is not lost.

Wavelength and the Notion of Invariance

We have argued in previous notes that the notion of wavelength for a free particle follows from the expression $-Et+px$ which is both the relativistic and nonrelativistic action = t^* Lagrangian with $v=x/t$ written in such a way that x and t are on the same footing. Thus $A=$ action= $-Et+px$. If $A=0$ is a global constant (which holds in different constantly moving frames) then there is a built-in clock and ruler for each constant p , namely t intervals are proportional to $1/E$ and x to $1/p$. This leads to the idea of a fixed length interval (wavelength) and time interval (frequency). Repeating the space units (independently of time) yields a probabilistic picture. This idea holds for both light and particles with rest mass.

The question is whether these wavelengths are physical. Interference experiments yield an affirmative answer. They also demonstrate that one need not consider smooth motion. For example an electron with constant p moves in a straight line which is smooth. It approaches a two slit system with the slits separated by about a wavelength. One then draws two rays (with different slopes), one from each slit to a fixed point on a screen beyond the slits. This is not a smooth scenario, but this is not an issue.

Wavelength of the Same Order as Lengths In a Bound System

A free particle which represents a constant velocity (and is linked to spatial invariance as $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar d/dx$) has a fixed characteristic length \hbar/p . A particle in a Newtonian bound system scheme has a constant p within a dx which is tiny compared to the length of the system. If \hbar/p is comparable to the overall length of the system, it does not fit within dx which is a problem. Quantum mechanics fixes this by insisting on:

- A. Conservation of energy at all x points i.e. within regions smaller than the wavelengths in the system.
- B. The presence of wavelengths
- C. Mathematical smoothness of kinetic energy at all x

The resulting approach is to create a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s such that they interfere to create a smooth x function representing an average kinetic energy i.e.

$$KE(x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W(x) \quad \text{with } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) = \text{smooth } x \text{ function}$$

$KE(x) + V(x) = E$ is applied, but leads to discrete E values. Thus smoothness in energy is broken, but matches experimental results. There is the further issue that:

$$-i\hbar dW/dx / W \text{ equal a momentum}(x) \text{ which is not equivalent to } p_{rms}(x) \text{ where } KE(x) = p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x)/2m$$

Thus interference of $\exp(ipx)$ s is needed to retain the idea of a wavelength yet at the same time create an average kinetic energy at each x point when added to $V(x)$ yields a constant because one cannot fit an $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. its wavelength into a dx in the problem.

Classical Limit

The idea of a classical limit from quantum mechanics seems to follow by taking the large energy level limit of solutions of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus one insists on the above A,B,C points holding. In the classical limit, however, the problem which led to the formation of:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$$

is no longer present. In the classical world, lengths are huge compared to \hbar/p . If one chooses a dx as representing "0", many $\hbar/p(x)$ values fit within dx . Thus the wavelength does not spill out of a dx region as it did in the quantum region. Thus one may have one p represented by several wavelengths within a dx , representing approximate spatial invariance and one may also have conservation of energy because one has $p(x)p(px)/2m + V(x)$ in one dx region and the same function in the next region yielding the same E . The only issue is that one no longer has smoothness of $W(x)$ which has become $\exp(ipx)$ or $\cos(px)$ with $p(x)$ changing in each dx region. Thus there is no need to have different $\exp(ipx)$ s interfering to describe a wavefunction which is smooth overall x . One may simply apply $\cos(px)$ to each dx with $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E$. This is the same result as decoherence. Interference of $\exp(ipx)$ s is only necessary when various wavelengths spill out a dx region and one needs a changing $p(x)$ (momentum) while still retaining the idea of wavelength in the problem. Even in the classical system a wavelength is present in each dx region, but it is tiny and so usually goes undetected except in the most sensitive of experiments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that both quantum bound states and classical Newtonian mechanics are based on the idea of conservation of energy. In Newtonian mechanics this is achieved by breaking space into equally spaced tiny dx regions such that kinetic energy and $V(x)$ change from one to the next. Quantum mechanics suggests that a particle with a fixed momentum is associated (due to spatial invariance) with a fixed length $\hbar/p = \text{wavelength}$. The problem which arises is that given a quantum system with a length L , a $dx \ll L$ is much smaller than \hbar/p . Thus one cannot have a constant p within this dx region because its wavelength does not "fit in". The quantum solution is to retain the notion of wavelength and conservation of energy at each x point, but create a mathematically smooth linear superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s i.e. a wavefunction $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Then an average kinetic energy $-1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx/W$ is forced to ensure conservation of energy even within regions smaller than the wavelength.

In this note we suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ does not need to be associated with smoothness. It is analogous to light which is not smooth when refracting or interfering in a two-slit system. $\exp(ipx)$ for a particle with rest mass is also not smooth when interfering in a two slit system. Thus $W(x) = \text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which is smooth is fine when wavelengths in question spill out of dx . If $p(x) = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ yields a wavelength which is tiny within a dx suitable to for length scales in a problem as is the case in the classical realm it seems there is no need to take a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s any longer. A single $\exp(ipx)$ or $\cos(px)$ for a given symmetry suffices within dx . This retains the idea of wavelength and approximate spatial invariance within dx and also conservation of energy from one dx to another. The only issue is that $\cos(px)$ is not smooth. It has one constant value in one dx region and another in the next. Like with refraction of light we argue this may not be a problem. It is as if the particle receives an almost instantaneous impulse when moving from one dx to another. This leads to the result of decoherence in the classical limit.